

MARKETING SHARE, MARKETING EFFICIENCY, MARKETING MARGIN, PRICE SPREAD OF TOMATO MARKETING CHANNELS IN RANGA REDDY DISTRICT, TELANGANA

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Abstract:

The present study on Study On Marketing Of Tomato In Ranga Reddy District Telangana was carried out during the session 2022-2023. The Descriptive research design was used in this study. Over all 100 respondents were selected by using random sampling method. The data were collected by personally interviewing the respondents with the help of structured questionnaire schedule. The data collected were carefully examined, classified, quantified, and tabulated. Frequencies, mean, standard deviation, percentage formula, marketing margin and cost of marketing were employed for interpreting the results. Marketing of tomato were estimated at grower level, during transportation, storage, wholesale, and retail trader level. This research is done to study the socio-economic conditions of farmers, marketing of mango in different stages, To identify the marketing channels, marketing cost, marketing efficiency, marketing share, marketing margin for tomato and the study was mainly aims to examine the constraints in marketing and suggest suitable measures to the farmers in the study area. The Producer who sold Tomato through the channel-I (Producer - Consumer) realized the highest share (87.66%) in consumer rupee as compared to other channels indicating the efficiency of channel compared to other channels. Small scale Tomato processing industry is growing significantly in Ranga Reddy district (3.82%) in terms of production and sale indicating potential opportunity for establishment of small-scale industries in district. Modern market infrastructure may be built in the regulated markets by the Telangana Board/State Government. Regular power supply may be ensured to the cold stores particularly in the summer months. The State/Union Government may provide financial/technical/logistic support to the tomato growers for cooperative/group marketing. Erratic electricity supply should be corrected so that farmers can adequately irrigate Tomato crop. The problem of shortage of labour can be countered by popularizing manually operating Tomato transplanted. Quality control of insecticide/pesticide should be ensured in the market so that farmers get quality products. The malpractices in the market should also be checked so that farmers get fair deal. Processing facilities should be developed.

Keywords: Marketing share, marketing efficiency, marketing margin, price spread, tomato

Introduction:

Tomato, scientifically known as *Solanum lycopersicum*, is a popular fruit that is widely used as a vegetable in various culinary preparations. Native to western South America, tomatoes belong to the nightshade family, Solanaceae. Tomato is an herbaceous sprawling plant growing to 1-3 m in height with weak woody stem. The flowers are yellow in colour and the fruits of cultivated varieties vary in size from cherry tomatoes, about 1–2 cm in size to beefsteak tomatoes, about 10 cm or more in diameter. Most cultivars produce red fruits when ripe. Tomato is a native to Peruvian and Mexican region. Tomato is one of the most important "protective foods" because of its special nutritive value. It is one of the most versatile vegetables with wide usage in Indian culture tradition. Tomatoes are used for soup, salad, pickles, ketchup, puree, sauces and in many other ways. It is also used as a salad vegetable. Tomato has very few competitors in the value addition chain of processing. Tomato is grown worldwide for local use or as an export crop. In 2014, the global area cultivated with tomato was 5 million hectares with a production of 171 million tonnes, the major tomato-producing

countries being the People's Republic of China and India. Tomato can be grown in a variety of geographical zones in open fields or greenhouses, and the fruit can be harvested by manual or mechanically.

Research Methodology:**Selection Of District:**

Among 31 districts of Telangana, Selection of the district was formed at the first stage of sampling. Ranga Reddy district of Telangana state was selected purposively for the present study.

Selection of the block

Selection of the block is the second stage of sampling; A complete list of blocks was taken out from the District Headquarters. Out of these, Pedavaram was selected randomly.

Selection of the village

Selection of the village is the third stage of the sampling. A complete list of the village of selected block was obtained from the Block Development Office of the concerned block. Out of total, 5 villages was selected randomly for the present study.

S.no	Villages	Respondents
1	Pedavaram.	26
2	Nandigama	11
3	Raghuvapuram	12
4	Satyavaram	10
5	Somavaram	10

Selection of the farmers

A complete list of 10% of farmers was proposed with the help of village head obtained randomly, and the selection of farmers are based on the farmers land holding.

The farmers were categorized on the bases of their holding size as:

- i. Marginal farmer group - below 1 ha

- ii. small farmer group - 1 to 2 ha
 iii. Semi- Medium farmer group - 2 to 4 ha
 iv. medium farmers - 4 to 10 ha
 v. large farmers - above 10 ha

All together 10% of farmers are selected in all 3 farm size groups in each selected village. Altogether total farmers were 100 viz, 51 small farmers, 32 medium farmers and 17 large farmers respectively.

Selection of Market and its functionaries:

Primary and secondary market was selected purposively, and all the market functionaries was selected randomly falling in the selected marketing channel the market functionaries was considered for data collection regarding and other marketing charges in different marketing channel list of all market functionaries will be prepared with list of all market functionaries was prepared.

Analytical Tools

Chi-square:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Where

C = Degree of freedom

O = Observed value (s)

E = Expected value (s)

Marketing Efficiency:

Marketing efficiency = V/I-1

V=output

I=input

Marketing cost :

Unit cost = variable cost + fixed cost / unit cost **Price spread:**

Marketing margin:

Marketing margin = Product price - Marketing Cost

Garrett's Ranking

Percent position = 100(Rij-0.5)/Nj

Rij stands for rank given for the ith factor by the jth individual

Nj stands for number of factors ranked by the individual.3.4.9

Market Share

Market share is calculated by taking the company's sales over the period and dividing it by the total sales of the company over the same period.

Marketing Efficiency

MME=FP/MC+MM

Where,

MME is modified measure of marketing efficiency FP=Price received by farmer

MC=Marketing cost MM=Marketing margin

Marketing cost

Marketing cost = C - Cf + Cml + Cm2 + Cm3 +... + Cmn

Price spread

Price spread = (Consumer price – Net price

of producer) * 100

Consumer price

Producer's Share in Consumer's Rupee:

Ps= Pf /Pc x 100

Where,

Ps=producer's share in consumer rupee.

Pf=price of produce received by the farmer.

Pc=price of produce paid by consumer.

Results And Discussions

Marketing Cost, Marketing Margin and Marketing Efficiency in channel I (Producer → Consumer)

Table 1.1 marketing cost, marketing margin, and price spread for channel I. This is the direct channel in which the producer sells his produce directly to the consumers without the involvement of any intermediaries. Average marketing cost when producers sold their produce to consumers in the market was Rs. 112.00 per quintal. Out of the total marketing cost incurred by the producer, wastage cost was highest (Rs. 70.00 /Qtl) followed by transportation costs amounting to Rs. 24.00 per quintal, packing charges Rs.12.00 per quintal and miscellaneous charges Rs. 6.00 per quintal, respectively. The sale price of the producer to consumers was Rs. 2000.00 per quintal in different farms size group. Net price received by the producers was Rs. 1888.00 per quintal which constitutes 94.40 per cent of the producer's share in consumer rupee. Marketing efficiency of the channel calculated by using Acharya approach was found to be 16.85 per cent which was high as compared to other channel

Sl. No.	Particulars	Value in Rupees/Qtl	
		Value (Rs.)	Percentage of the consumer's price
1	Producer sale price to Consumers	2000	100.00
2	Cost Incurred by the producer		
i	Transportation cost	24.00	1.20
ii	Packing charges	12.00	0.60
iii	Wastage cost	70.00	3.50
iv	Miscellaneous charges	6.00	0.30
3	Total Cost Incurred by the producers (i- iv)	112.00	2.10
4	Net price received by the producers	1888.00	92.95
5	Price Spread	112.00	52.00
6	Producer's share in consumer rupee (%)	46.20	94.40
7	Marketing Efficiency (%)	8.00	16.85

Marketing Cost, Marketing Margin and Marketing Efficiency in channel II (Producer → Retailer → Consumer)

Sl. No.	Particulars	Value in Rupees/Qtl		Sl. No.
		Value (Rs.)	Percentage	
1	Producer sale price to Retailers	1400.00	56.00	
2	Cost Incurred by the producer			
i	Transportation cost	20.00	0.80	
ii	Loading, Unloading, Weighting	10.00	0.40	
iii	Wastage cost	70.00	2.80	
iv	Miscellaneous charges	6.00	0.24	
3	Total Cost Incurred by the producers (i-iv)	106.00	1.44	

4	Net price received by the Producers	1294.00	51.76
5	Sale price of producers to Retailers	1400.00	56.00
6	Cost Incurred by retailers		
I	Loading, Unloading, Weighting	10.00	0.40
II	Transportation cost	25.00	1.00
III	Shop/Rehri charges	16.00	0.64
IV	Packing cost	10.00	0.40
V	Wastage cost	42.00	1.68
VI	Miscellaneous expenses	6.00	0.24
7	Total cost incurred by retailers (i-vi)	109.00	2.68
8	Retailer's margin	991.00	41.32
9	Retailers' sale price to consumers	2500.00	100
10	Price Spread	1206.00	500.00
11	Producer's share in consumer rupee (%)	25.36	51.76

Table 1.2 In the second marketing channel of tomato, the producer sells his produce to the retailer in the local market. The retailer takes produce to a nearby market and sells it to the end consumer. Various costs incurred and the margin earned in this channel is presented in table 4.3.2 The total cost incurred by the producer was found to be Rs.106.00 per quintal, in which maximum cost incurred was wastage cost was highest (Rs.70.00 /quintal) followed by transportation i.e., Rs. 20.00 per quintal, loading and unloading charges Rs.10.00 per quintal and market fee of Rs. 6.00 per quintal, respectively. The average selling price of the producer to the retailer was Rs. 1400.00per quintal while the net price received by the producer was

Rs. 1294.00 which constituted 51.76 per cent of the consumer's price. The total average cost incurred by the retailer on was Rs. 109.00 per quintal, which included Transportation cost (Rs.25.00 /quintal), Shop/Rehri charges (Rs. 16.00 /quintal), packing cost (Rs.10.00 /quintal) and miscellaneous expenses (Rs. 6.00 /quintal). The retailer sold the produce to the final consumer at Rs. 2500.00 per quintal after earning the margin of Rs. 991.00 per quintal. The overall price spread in Channel II was Rs.1206.00 per quintal and the marketing efficiency of this channel was found to be 1.07 per cent.

Marketing Cost, Marketing Margin and Price Spread in channel III (Producer→ Wholesaler→ Retailer → Consumer)

Sl. No.	Particulars	Value (Rs. /Qtl)	Percentage (%)
1	Producer sale price to Wholesalers	1200	42.86
2	Cost Incurred by the producer		
I	Loading charge	8.00	0.29
ii	Wastage cost	68.40	2.42
iii	Miscellaneous expenses	6.00	0.21
3	Total Cost Incurred by the producers	82.40	0.50
4	Net price received by the producers	1117.60	39.91
5	Purchase price of wholesalers	1200.00	42.86
6	Costs incurred by the wholesalers		
i	Unloading charge	12.00	0.43
ii	Transportation charge	110.00	3.93
iii	Cooling/Ripening Charge	90.00	3.21
iv	Wastage cost	102.00	3.64
v	Miscellaneous expenses	8.00	0.29
7	Total cost incurred by the wholesaler (i-v)	322.00	7.86
8	Wholesaler's Margin	178.00	10.00
9	Sale Price of wholesaler to Retailers	1700.00	60.71
10	Cost Incurred by the retailers		
i	Transportation	66.60	2.38
ii	Rent for Shop/ Rehri	16.00	0.57
iii	Packing cost	10.00	0.36
iv	Wastage cost	68.00	2.42
v	Miscellaneous expenses	6.00	0.21
11	Total Cost Incurred by the retailer(i-v)	166.60	3.52
12	Retailer's Margin	933.40	35.76
13	Sale price of Retailers to Consumers	2800.00	100.00
14	Price Spread	1682.40	800.20
15	Producer's share in consumer rupee	16.45	39.91

	(%)		
16	Marketing Efficiency	5.26	10.66

Table 1.3 the third marketing channel, the wholesaler himself approaches the producer and purchases their produce at field level directly and takes produce to the wholesale market and disposes it to the retailers. The marketing cost and the marketing margin of the producer and the intermediary of marketing is shown in table 4.8. The price spread analysis of this channel reveals that the total average cost incurred by the producer included wastage cost (Rs. 68.40/quintal) followed by on loading charges (Rs. 8.00 /Qtl) and miscellaneous charges (Rs.6.00 /quintal). The producer sold the produce to the wholesaler at a price of Rs. 1200 per quintal. The net price received by the producer was Rs. 1117.60 per quintal which accounts for 39.91 per cent of the consumer's rupee. The cost incurred by the wholesaler was Rs.322.00 per quintal. The major components of wholesaler's expenditure include transportation cost (Rs.110.00 /quintal), wastage cost (102/quintal) Loading/unloading (Rs.12.00/quintal) and cooling charge (Rs. 90.00 /quintal) respectively. The margin of the wholesaler

accounted for Rs. 178.00 per quintal. The wholesaler further sold the produce to the retailer at Rs. 1700.00 per quintal. The cost incurred by the retailer was Rs. 166.60 per quintal which includes wastage cost (Rs. 68.00 /quintal), shop/Rehri charge (Rs. 16.00 /quintal), transportation cost (Rs. 66.60 /quintal), Packing cost (Rs.10.00 /quintal) and miscellaneous expenses (Rs. 6.00 /quintal). The retailer finally sells the produce to the end consumer at Rs. 2800 per quintal after adding his margin of Rs. 933.00 per quintal. The price spread in this channel, which is the difference between price paid by the consumer and price received by the producer is Rs. 1682.40 per quintal while the marketing efficiency was estimated to be 0.66 per cent.

Marketing Cost, Marketing Margin and Marketing Efficiency in Channel IV(Producer→ Commission agent → Wholesaler → Retailer → Consumer)

Sl. No.	Particulars	Value in Rupees/Qts	
		Value (Rs.)	Percentage (%)
1	Producer sale price to Commission Agents	1350.00	48.21
2	Cost Incurred by the producer		
I	Loading and unloading	20.00	0.71
II	Transportation	110.00	3.93
III	Commission charge @ten per Cent	135.00	4.82
IV	Wastage cost	75.60	2.70
V	Miscellaneous expenses	6.00	0.21
3	Total Cost incurred by the producer (i-v)	346.60	12.38
4	Net price received by the Producer	1003.40	35.84
5	Purchase price of commission Agents	1350.00	48.21
6	Cost Incurred by Commission Agents		
I	Precooling expenses	90.00	3.21
II	Miscellaneous Expenses	10.00	0.36
7	Total cost incurred by Commission Agents	100.00	3.57
8	Commission agent's Margin	50.00	1.79
9	Sale Price of commission agents to Wholesalers	1500.00	53.57
10	Cost Incurred by the Wholesalers		
I	Loading/Unloading	22.00	0.79
II	Transportation	60.00	2.14
	Wastage cost	90.00	3.21
III	Miscellaneous expenses	8.00	0.29
11	Total Cost incurred by the Wholesalers	180.00	6.43
12	Wholesaler's Margin	170.00	6.07
13	Sale price of Wholesalers to Retailers	1850.00	66.07
14	Cost Incurred by Retailer's		
I	Transportation	66.60	2.38
II	Rent for Shop/ Rehri	16.00	0.57
III	Packing cost	10.00	0.36
IV	Wastage cost	83.28	2.97
V	Miscellaneous expenses	6.00	0.21
15	Total Cost incurred by retailers	181.85	6.49
16	Retailer's Margin	768.15	27.43
17	Retailer's sale price to consumers	2800.00	100.00
18	Price Spread	1796.60	800.26
19	Producer's share in consumer rupee (%)	16.42	35.84
20	Marketing Efficiency	5.23	10.55

Table 1.4 The fourth marketing channel, producer sent their produce to commission agent in the wholesale mandi situated in Bhilai powerhouse. The commission agent sells the produce to the distant

wholesaler at the commission of 10 per cent. The commission agent thereby disposes the produce to the distant wholesalers which is further sold to the retailers of nearby market. Various costs and

margins involved in channel IV are shown in table 4.3.4 The total cost incurred by grower was Rs.346.60 per quintal and includes wastage cost (Rs. 75.60 /quintal), loading/unloading charges (Rs. 20.00/quintal), transportation (Rs. 110.00 /quintal) and commission charges (Rs. 135.00/quintal). The net price received by the banana grower was Rs. 1003.40 per quintal which accounts for 35.84 per cent of the consumer's rupee. The grower sells the produce to the commission agent at a price of Rs. 1350.00 /quintal. The total cost incurred by the commission agent was Rs.100.00 per quintal. The major components of commission agent's expenditure include ripening/cooling charge (Rs.90.00 /quintal). The margin of the commission agent accounted for Rs. 50.00 per quintal. The commission agent then forwards the produce to the distant wholesaler at Rs. 1500.00 per quintal. The cost incurred by the distant wholesaler amounts to Rs.180.00 per quintal which includes wastage cost (Rs.90.00 /quintal), loading/unloading charge (Rs. 22.00 /quintal), transportation cost (Rs. 60.00 /quintal) and miscellaneous expenses (Rs. 8.00 /quintal). The distant wholesaler gets the margin of Rs. 170.00 per quintal. The distant wholesaler sells the produce to the retailer at Rs. 1850.00 per quintal. The cost incurred by the retailer amounts to Rs. 181.85 per quintal which includes wastage cost (Rs.83.28/quintal), shop/Rehri charge (Rs. 16.00 /quintal) and transportation cost (Rs. 66.60/quintal), packing cost (Rs. 10.00 /quintal) and miscellaneous expenses (Rs. 6.00/quintal). The retailer adds his margin of Rs. 768.15per quintal and sells the produce to the end consumer at Rs. 2800.00 per quintal. The price spread on this channel amounted to Rs. 1796.60 per quintal. The marketing efficiency of this channel was estimated to be 0.55 per cent. Thus, the above analysis clearly shows that the longer the channel and more the number of intermediaries in the system, bigger the price spread and the share of producer in consumer rupee declines. The above results are in accordance with the findings of Shrode (2009) and Pawar et. al. (2010) and Naveen et. al. (2015) who also gave similar results in their study on supply chain efficiency of banana.

Conclusion:

The Producer who sold Tomato through the channel-I (Producer - Consumer) realized the highest share (87.66%) in consumer rupee as compared to other channels indicating the efficiency of channel compared to other channels. Small scale Tomato processing industry is growing significantly in Ranga Reddy district (3.82%) in terms of production and sale indicating potential opportunity for establishment of small-scale industries in district. The extension agencies may educate the farmers, particularly the small and marginal ones regarding the seed rate, latest varieties of tomato crop, seed replacement schedule, selection of seed and its storage, chemical treatment before sowing, etc. Modern market infrastructure may be built in the regulated markets by the Telangana Board/State Government. Regular power supply may be ensured to the cold stores particularly in the summer months. Quality testing laboratory for tomato may be set up at in Nandigama. It will help the tomato growers/traders in the export of the produce. The State/Union Government may provide financial / technical/logistic support to the tomato growers for cooperative/group marketing. Erratic electricity supply should be corrected so that farmers can adequately irrigate Tomato crop. The problem of shortage of labour can be countered by popularizing manually operating Tomato transplanted. The farmers can avoid distress sales by availing warehouse receipt loans. Quality control of insecticide/pesticide should be ensured in the market so that farmers get quality products. The malpractices in the market

should also be checked so that farmers get fair deal. Processing facilities should be developed.

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